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Document Overview

1. Objectives and Team

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR)¹ for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Within the structure of the ITSERR project, the Work Package 8 (WP8)–*uBIQUity*, which incorporates the “BI” of the Bible(s) and the “QU” of the Qur’ān in its title, aims at investigating the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam in different environments and historical periods through two huge *corpora*: Greek and Latin Christian commentaries (broadly understood as exegetical works) on the Bible(s) written from the Patristic age until the Late Byzantine period, and classical commentaries on the Qur’ān written in Arabic (*tafāsīr*) from the rise of Islam until the 15th century.

These works are unique sources for the study of knowledge, readings, and hermeneutics of the sacred texts through the centuries. The intertextual references, conscious or unconscious, that the ancient commentaries contain work as invisible “places of memory”, thus making sacred texts “ubiquitous” (hence the title of the project). When recontextualized for new audiences and readers, the references to a sacred text undergo a transformation that may affect the form and/or meaning ascribed to them. At the same time, they retain a traceable connection to their source text, at least for those still able to grasp it.

By interweaving the research methods of the Humanities and state-of-the-art Computer Science research, *uBIQUity* is developing a novel research tool that can identify references to the Bible(s), the Qur’ān, and the *’ahādīṭ* (the Sayings of the Prophet) in ancient Christian and Islamic exegetical works with a higher degree of accuracy than pre-existing resources.

The WP8 team members are:

- Sara **ABRAM**, University of Palermo (UNIPA): Arabic texts.
- Marcello **COSTA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabrizio **D’AVENIA**, WP8 Leader, UNIPA.
- Cinzia **FERRARA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Anna **MAMBELLI**, WP8 Scientific Coordinator and Product Owner, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE): Greek and Latin texts.
- Chiara **PALILLO**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabio **TUTRONE**, UNIPA: Latin texts.

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), University of Naples L’Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA), and University of Torino (UNITO).

Regarding research in the field of Computer Science, for the Latin section, the collaboration with the UNIMORE team composed of Davide **CAFFAGNI**, Federico **COCCHI**, Marcella **CORNIA**, Rita **CUCCHIARA**, and also with Cesare **CONCORDIA** and Carlo **MEGHINI** of the National Research Council (CNR) is fundamental. As for the Arabic section of WP8, Giovanni **PUCETTI** of the CNR is working on the IT side.

Concerning research and work on Ancient Greek, WP8 has decided to collaborate with the team of another project with similar aims, which has been incubated in the framework of RESILIENCE RI, namely the PRIN (Italian Research Project of National Interest, n. 20229E83B3) *Resilient Septuagint. An Initial Exploration of the Semantics of Killing and Healing in the Septuagint and its Reception in Patristic and Late Antique Sources (3rd cent. BCE-5th cent. CE)*. This PRIN project involves the *Alma Mater Studiorum* University of Bologna (UNIBO, PI Research Unit), the University of Bari (UNIBA), and the University of Catania (UNICT). The *Resilient Septuagint* team members are: Luca **ARCARI** (University of Naples Federico II), Laura **BIGONI** (UNIBO), Laura **CARNEVALE** (UNIBA Research Unit Chief), Davide **DAINESE** (Principal Investigator [PI], UNIBO), Isabella **PIGNOCCO** (UNICT), Arianna **ROTONDO** (UNICT Research Unit Chief and deputy PI), Giorgia **SAMPÒ** (DDC University of Southern Denmark-UNIBO), Gianluca **SCATIGNO** (UNIBO), and Marco **ZANELLA** (University of Padua-UNIBO). This collaboration between WP8 and *Resilient Septuagint* has included and will continue to include the development of a shared methodological framework and interoperable datasets for the study of Greek biblical texts and their heritage.

This document is the second deliverable from the WP8 of ITSERR (D8.1.2) and describes the operational functioning of *uBIQUity*, intended as a software that runs the algorithms described in D8.1.1 (first deliverable). Originally, this software was intended to be provided on two twin websites (one for the texts of Christianity, the other for the sources of Islam) hosted on a shared platform, but in the course of the work on *uBIQUity*, the scientific need emerged to create a single software with the three languages included in the project: Ancient Greek, Latin and Arabic. More specifically, this whitepaper focuses on User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI) Design and shows the types of operations that researchers can perform on the above-mentioned *corpora* according to their scientific needs. It underlines the efforts of the *uBIQUity* transdisciplinary team in providing new ways of visualizing, exploring, and producing knowledge according to different cognitive styles.

From the UX/UI Design perspective, this document analyses the benefits of node-based user interfaces on the *uBIQUity* platform and emphasizes the importance of a qualitative approach versus a quantitative one for Artificial Intelligence (AI)-supported text comparisons. Since thinking processes in digital text analysis are lost in the outputs of current AI text-based user interfaces, keeping track of them allows for an interpretive approach. Within the User Experience and Data Visualization Design framework, we are developing a platform that uses a node-based UI to manage and display data, as well as to compare textual passages through workflows that remain stored. The *uBIQUity* platform

emphasizes collaborative knowledge-building and supports different cognitive learning styles. By combining Philology, History, Exegesis, Computer Science, Computational Linguistics, and Design, it overcomes the limitations of tools based solely on quantitative analysis, offering flexible interactions with digitized texts.

The emerging spread of AI tools produces results that lack structure, are often difficult to review, contain visual clutter, and incur context-switching costs due to their linear, text-based user interfaces. ChatGPT and other systems that leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) algorithms have limitations in managing information complexity. Their conversational interfaces based on sequential generation of texts do not allow an easy view of the search flow or a hierarchical structuring of the collected information, often resulting in cognitive overload. The *uBIQUity* platform aims to provide researchers with a new research tool that exploits the potential of AI, while at the same time developing an interpretative approach that enhances their cognitive capabilities instead of limiting them.

The last section of this document (“Algorithms and IT tools”) provides preliminary information on precisely this tool and on the results of the operations carried out with it, the aspects of which will be analyzed in more detail in the deliverable D8.1.3 devoted to showing the effectiveness of algorithms.

2. Scope

As stated in D.8.1.1, what the project is interested in is not sheer literary and quantitative data. Rather, this research on references to a sacred text, understood as invisible “places of memory”/*lieux de mémoire* embedded in exegetical works, focuses on reconstructing the individual and collective “memories” and the traditions of religious communities over time and space, as well as exploring the recurrent exegetical methods used by the cultured members of these communities. The two aspects are closely connected, as authoritative interpretations of sacred texts shape memories, beliefs, and practices within faith communities, and their oscillation can lead to shifts in religious identities. In a diametrically opposed yet complementary direction, the research conducted within *uBIQUity* could also show whether there are (and what are) verses or passages of sacred texts that have been “deprived” of their heritage, not quoted or used by later authors, and thus fell into the oblivion of time.

Precisely because the research questions focus on data quality and interpretation rather than quantity, the transdisciplinary WP8 team has been instrumental in bringing together and meeting both the needs of the interpretive approach of the (digital and non-digital) Humanities and the analytical requirements of digital technologies. The collaborative nature of the project allows the WP8 team as a whole to transcend the limitations of individual disciplines and formulate research questions that otherwise could not be realized.

Each discipline offers a unique perspective and contributes to the overall result. Philologists and historians of the WP8 team bring their expertise in understanding and interpreting ancient texts, identifying linguistic and semantic nuances, and exegetical methods; computational linguists provide methods for semantic tagging and morphological analysis; computer scientists create algorithms that can handle complex language patterns; and designers ensure that the resulting digital tools are accessible and visually coherent. The field of Religious Studies is well suited to this type of interaction, due to its transdisciplinary nature, diachrony, multilingualism, and the complexity of its subject matter.

Producing knowledge on filigrees of sacred texts is the main but not sole goal of the *uBIQUity* project. This knowledge must be made automatically findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by machines and individuals (see Wilkinson, Dumontier, Aalbersberg *et alii* 2016; cf. also <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>). To this end, visualization and interaction within the entire (re)search process become crucial, as the following sections will show.

3. State of the Art

Over the past fifteen years, several tools have been developed that serve the objectives of *uBIQUity*. The analysis of these tools, together with contacts with various projects and research centers responsible for their development, constituted the preliminary and foundational work of the WP8 team (see also the first deliverable D8.1.1). Today, scholars have access to an extraordinary collection of literary and exegetical heritage in digital format. This also includes resources such as dictionaries and lexicons, translations, automatic lemmatization of inflected forms, N-grams, and concordances, all of which are extremely helpful. A key tool for finding biblical references in patristic works is *BiblIndex* (<https://www.biblindex.org/en>), which, however, has some limitations: it does not perform a direct search in the texts, but only relies on the biblical passages identified as such by the editors of each work and redirects users to the pages and paragraphs of the printed editions.

The list below, compiled by the WP8 team, is not exhaustive, but it conveys the richness of these pre-existing resources while highlighting a problem faced by scholars of ancient texts, particularly sacred texts: the lack of a unified platform that combines textual resources with advanced technologies for detecting intertextual references.

Sources	Text reuse	Semantic search
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perseus Digital Library + Scaife Viewer of Perseus Project (Gregory R. Crane; https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/; https://scaife.perseus.org/) Theosaurus Linguae Graecae (TLG; https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/) Theosaurus Linguae Latinae (ThL; https://tll.degruyter.com/; https://thesaurus.baw.de/tll-digital/tll-open-access.html) Bibliotheca Teubneriana Latina-2 (BTI-2; http://www.degruyter.com/databases/tbi.html) Packard Humanities Institute CD-5 (PHIS; https://packham.org/) for Classical Latin texts, some biblical texts also in other languages, and Greek inscriptions Library of Latin Texts (LLT; https://www.brepols.net/series/LLT/O-includes-Corpus-Christiannum-Series-Latina-[CCLC]) Theosaurus Formorum (TF-CLE; https://www.brepols.net/series/TF) Vetus Latina Database (VLD; https://www.brepols.net/series/vld-o) Clavis Clavium (https://about.brepols.net/clavis-clavium/) Poetria Nova incorporates the Poetria CD corpus Corpus Corporum (Philipp Roelli; https://mlat.uzh.ch/) includes PL and a synopsis of the biblical versions Digital Latin Library (https://digitallatin.org/) Open Greek and Latin (https://www.opengreekandlatin.org/) IntraText Digital Library (https://www.intratext.com/inap.htm) Göttinger Synagoga database (https://synagoga.uni-goettingen.de/) Hexapla Project (https://hexapla.org/) – the project material will be integrated into the digital archive of the Göttingen team Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, Stuttgart (https://www.bibelwissenschaft.de/bibel/LATX/GFN/1) BibleWorks (https://www.bibleworks.com/) Logos Bible Software is developed by Faithlife Corporation (https://www.logos.com/) Accordance Bible Software (https://www.accordancebible.com/) Novum Testamentum Patristicum, Universität Regensburg (https://www.uni-regensburg.de/theologie/novum-testamentum-patristicum/home/index.html; https://www.vr-elibrary.de/series/nfta) Papyri and inscriptions (https://papyri.info/; https://www.trismegistos.org/lang/; https://inscriptions.packhum.org/; DBMNT https://www.dbmnet.uni.edu.de/; https://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/lgpn-link for etymology and semantics of person names in ancient Greek) Digital Corpus for Graeco-Arabic Studies (https://www.graeco-arabic-studies.org/home.html) IslamWeb General Knowledge (https://gk.islamweb.net/) Al-Maktaba al-Shamīyah (https://shamela.ws/category/3) al-Tajīr (https://www.al-tajir.com/index.asp) Sunnah (https://sunnah.com/) Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (OpenITI; https://openiti.org/) Linked Open Tafsiir (https://conf.crcncopenitafsiir.com/; https://tafsiirabari.com/; https://scholarship.org/2022/eodmg/1.330; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R8hcyRaic08ub_chouna1-FrankforterKoranstafian) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tracor (Marco Bächtler; https://www.etrn.eu/research/tracor/; for Greek, Latin and Arabic) Tesseract version 5 (Neil Coffee; https://tesseract.casert.unifi.edu/; for Greek and Latin) BibliIndex project (https://www.bibliindex.org/en) led by Sources Christianes CoreNLP is created by Natural Language Processing Group at Stanford University (https://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/) CLARIN-IT-ER (https://www.eurocl.ac.uk/institutes-centers/istituto-di-linguistica-applicata/progetti/clarin-it-er) and LIT (https://www.eurocl.ac.uk/institutes-centers/institute-for-applied-linguistics/projects/it) Biblical Online Synopsis (https://biblicalonlinesynopsis.com/) KIT-IB (Sarah Bowen Savant, Aga Khan University; https://kitab-project.org/) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perseus Hopper (https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/morphological-analyzer/) Theosaurus Linguae Graecae (TLG; http://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/) including the following dictionaries: <i>Liddell-Scott-Jones Greek-English Lexicon</i> (https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/lsg/); <i>Lexicon tur byzantino-schone Græcæ</i> (https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/lbg/) For the dictionaries, cf. <i>The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek Online</i> (https://dictionaries.brillonline.com/search/dictionary-&id-) For expanded lexicons of Ancient and Byzantine Greek, cf. <i>Words in Progress</i> (http://www.aristarchus.unige.net/Wordsinprogress-IT/Home) F.R. Adrados (dir.), <i>Dictionario Griego-Español</i> (http://dce.ub.edu/sde/) <i>Historical and Theological Lexicon of the Septuagint</i> (https://www.litsec.it/lang/eng/rostra/canibri/document/162095931); electronic edition? <i>Theosaurus Linguae Latinae</i> (TLL; https://tll.degruyter.com/; https://thesaurus.baw.de/tll-digital/tll-open-access.html) CLTK, GLEM, RNN Tagger, and Satoro are the 4 existing lemmatizers for ancient Greek (Colin Swaenens, Ilse De Vos, Els Lefever - Universiteit Gent) Latin WordNet (Stefano Mimozzi; https://ila-erc.eu/data/lexicalResources/LatinWordNet/Lexicon; https://latinwordnet.eveter.ac.uk/; for synset) ILIA: Linking Latin (https://ila-erc.eu/?page-top; https://ila-erc.eu/T/ia/asp/) collects and connects both existing and newly-generated (metadata). The former are mostly linguistic resources (corpora, lexica, ontologies, dictionaries, thesauri) and NLP tools (tokenisers, lemmatisers, POS-tagger, morphological analysers and dependency parsers) for Latin. ILIA also improves the lexical coverage of the <i>Latin WordNet</i> Open Ancient Greek WordNet (OAGWN) (https://dipac-clarin.fr/ils/ent/its/monitors/omni/handle/20.500.11752.11.C.56; https://dipac-clarin.fr/ for synset) and <i>Linked WordNets for Ancient Indo-European languages</i> (https://sites.google.com/jumipr.it/linked-wordnets-home-page) UPC Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (https://www.talp.upc.edu/content/wordnet-mappings-automatically-generated-mappings-among-wordnet-versions) Papyri and inscriptions (https://papyri.info/; https://www.trismegistos.org/lang/; https://inscriptions.packhum.org/; DBMNT https://www.dbmnet.uni.edu.de/; https://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/lgpn-link for etymology and semantics of person names in ancient Greek) CATSS (= Computer Assisted Tools for Septuagint Studies, co-directors: Emanuel Tov, Hebrew University, and Robert Kraft, University of Pennsylvania; https://cat.sas.upenn.edu/rnk/cats.html; http://cat.sas.upenn.edu/gopher/text/reigion/biblical/xxmorph/) is a lemmatizer already calibrated on the LXX ASTAGS project (Automated Semantic Tagging of the Göttingen Septuagint Apparatus) of Tuukka Kahvanen and Hannu Kalavainen (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/the-septuagint-and-its-ancient-versions; chrome-extension://efaidhbnmmhpeapeglglefindmka/https://jtrc.org/v25-TC-2020-Kahvanen-Kalavainen.pdf) Synacticus (https://synacticus.org/ for Parsing trees on the New Testament) Almaany (https://www.almaany.com/; dictionaries, translations, synset) Ejool (https://ejool.net/; comparative searches across multiple dictionaries simultaneously) Lang Arabic-English Lexicon (https://lexicon.queens-research.net/) ElizaFM (https://quest.ms.mff.cuni.cz/cgi-bin/elizfm/index.fcgi?mode=home; tokenization and morphological analysis) Quranic Arabic Corpus (https://corpus.quran.com/; morphological annotation, syntactic treebank, and semantic ontology) Linked Open Tafsiir (research based on topic, individual, sura, etc.) Mutan.io Corpus Builder (https://www.mutan.io/?fbclid=IwAR0TWL0ahR3W1G085Z)

Tab. 0: Selected existing resources relevant to WP8. Projects and research centers with which the uBIQUiity team has established contact are highlighted in yellow.

The WP8 team also examined some computational tools developed in other fields to assess their potential usefulness, particularly with respect to functionality for integrating diverse needs and technologies. In this type of analysis, the contribution of computer scientists and designers was essential, since many of the tools with which humanists are unfamiliar employ interfaces that are far from intuitive for them. Johanna Drucker observes that humanists frequently experience discomfort when using tools from other disciplines, especially those that are inflexible and not aligned with the interpretive approach their research demands. Additionally, she emphasizes that a common user-as-consumer model is not “appropriate for analyzing a humanities-based experience (where goals of distraction, engagement, flow experience, and pleasure-driven activities are not goal-oriented but motivated by the process)” (Drucker 2020, p. 11). Knowledge is not a product to be delivered.

The data collected, produced, processed, stored and used in the uBIQUiity project are granular textual data queried through complex, dynamic and multidimensional search operations, as is inherent to the research field of Religious Studies. Therefore, from a design perspective, two main questions have arisen: How can we represent scientific knowledge in this field and how can we interact with it?

First, we must consider the fact that, beyond the specific field of research, human reasoning often follows non-linear, associative and context-dependent paths (Costa 2025; see section 10 of this deliverable). Although AI tools can assist in organizing and modelling such reasoning, their outputs are frequently constrained by design choices, especially when implemented through linear, text-based interfaces. This disconnect between the non-linear,

interpretive nature of human reasoning and the often-rigid structure of AI interfaces and statistical tools reveals a deeper challenge: even when computational resources are available, they may remain opaque or misaligned with the goals of humanistic research. This is particularly evident in quantitative analyses, which may offer visually compelling results but lack interpretability for both creators and audiences (cf. Stella 2018, p. 15). Bridging this gap requires rethinking the way we design digital tools, not only from a technical perspective, but also from a humanistic one.

Secondly, if we aim to ground our work in an interpretive perspective, it is essential to recognize that what we call “data” are not neutral or purely factual. As Drucker (2011) suggests, they are better understood as *capta*, information that has been selected, framed and constructed through processes of observation and interpretation. This conceptually useful distinction becomes especially relevant in fields such as Philology, History, and Religious Studies, where textual evidence is never raw but already mediated by layers of editorial, critical and historical decisions. Rather than treating *data* and *capta* as fixed and opposing categories, we propose understanding them as points on a continuum of interpretive complexity—one that calls for visual methods and tools which, through a humanistic lens, foreground ambiguity, variation, and epistemological transparency.

In this context, design fields such as User Experience Design and Data Visualization play a crucial role in providing different and broader perspectives that incorporate real humanistic methodologies, while taking advantage of the emerging capabilities of AI.

4. Methodology

To begin addressing questions about how to represent and interact with knowledge within the *uBIQUity* project, the WP8 designers attempted to formalize one of the basic workflows used by Religious Studies specialists in comparing ancient religious texts.

Fig. 1: Basic workflow for comparing ancient Bible versions and commentaries in Latin.

This also enabled the development of a shared glossary and helped familiarize the entire interdisciplinary team with established philological, exegetical, and historical methods used in the study of intertextuality, including step-by-step research procedures, sources, and working tools. To explore the connections between actors and actions in more depth, we pursued three parallel lines of research: (1) user research based on surveys and interviews [section 4.1]; (2) collection of user stories to define more detailed scenarios and workflows [section 4.2]; and (3) textual analysis to formalize the structures of the Scriptures and commentaries to be integrated into the *uBIQUity* platform [section 4.3].

4.1 User Research

To ensure the integration of scientific knowledge into the design process, it is essential to establish a methodological framework that is meticulously tailored to various qualitative and quantitative research phases of the project (Maldonado 2015, p. 154). The aims of *uBIQUity* require and inspire a defined methodological approach that incorporates techniques from allied disciplines in harmony with the project's transdisciplinary nature. In terms of design, this implies first adapting a system to people's different cognitive styles and ways of interacting with knowledge, and then reimagining their workflows in a digital environment by writing the so-called "user stories."

Recognizing different cognitive styles requires analyzing individual learning patterns through structured interviews and focus groups. Specifically, we prepared a questionnaire (using Google Form) based on the VARK (= Visual, Aural, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic) model, which was introduced by Neil D. Fleming to enhance the learning experiences of his students and to explore and categorize the ways and strategies through which data and information are recorded and processed by individuals (Fleming 2001). Our questionnaire was filled out by 29 participants, both internal and external to the ITSERR project (76.5% researchers, 11.9% PhD fellows, 5.8% associate professors, 5.8% full professors), aged between 25 and 55, from different academic fields: Religious Studies, Classics, History, Philosophy, and Law.

The first part of the interview format (*Researcher's work. A survey of places, methods and tools for humanistic research*) was organized into six thematic sections (*Background Information, Context, Spaces, Tools, Time, and New Knowledge*) and included both open- and closed-ended questions. This specific structure allowed for the identification of the needs, requirements, challenges, and aspirations expressed by the scientific community. In particular, the inclusion of open-ended questions provided detailed insights into the more complex dimensions of researchers' activities.

The questions used in the first part of the interview process are listed below.

TAB. 1	
	Researcher's work. A survey of places, methods and tools for humanistic research.
	Background information
1	Age <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25-35 • 35-45 • 45-55 • 55-65
2	What role do you play in the ITSERR project? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD student • Researcher • Associate Professor • Full Professor
	Context. We are curious to know your research activity and what you love most about your work.
3	What's your professional background?
4	Indicates your scientific disciplinary field of reference.
5	What is the specialization of your research?
6	Summarize step by step what your research work consists of.
7	Briefly describe your research activity for ITSERR.
8	What do you love most in your work and why?
	Places. Help us visualize where you are doing your research.
9	Where do you do your research?
10	Describe your place of study.
11	Which objects (bookshelf, desk, computer, etc) in your study are important to you and your work?
12	Are you able to carry out research activities remotely? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No (skip to question number 21)
13	Where do you usually work remotely? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home • More
14	Describe your workplace remotely.

15	Do you prefer to work in presence or remotely? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In presence ● Remotely ● In both ways
16	Why?
17	Which of the two works is more functional for you? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In presence ● Remotely ● In both ways
18	Why?
19	Is it more comfortable for you to work in presence or remotely? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In presence ● Remotely ● In both ways
20	Why?
21	On a scale of 1 to 5, how important is the workplace to you? 1 2 3 4 5
22	On a scale of 1 to 5, how important is a functional workplace to you? 1 2 3 4 5
23	On a scale of 1 to 5, how important is a cozy workplace? 1 2 3 4 5
	Tools. Even a small object can make a difference and tell the story of who uses it. Describe what tools you use for your research.
24	What tools do you use in your search? Sort them into a list according to your priorities.
25	Do you prefer Analog or digital tools for your research activities? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Analog ● Digital ● Both
26	State the reasons for your preference.
27	Generally, in your research work you usually take notes? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No (skip to question number 33)
28	In what timeframe? 1 2 3 4 5

29	<p>Do you prefer to take notes using a digital tool (tablet, computer, etc.) or an Analog tool (notepad, post-it, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analog • Digital
30	Why?
31	<p>Taking notes in a notebook while using your computer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No (skip to question number 33)
32	Why don't you write them down on a digital device?
33	What are your digital skills and abilities?
34	<p>On a scale of 1 to 5, if you had to quantify your computer skills, what value would you indicate?</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
35	Do you use search software? Which ones?
36	<p>On a scale of 1 to 5, if you had to quantify your experience in using software or programs for research, what value would you indicate?</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
37	<p>How would you define the digital interfaces you use?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-intuitive • Intuitive
38	<p>How would you define the functionality of the digital tools you use?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deficient • Enough • Optimal
39	<p>Do you also use other devices (tablets, smartphones, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No (skip to question number 41)
40	Which ones?
41	<p>Do you use digitized texts for research purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
42	<p>In order to make the work of the researcher even easier to use, do you think digitized texts can be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No (skip to question number 44)

43	How?
44	Why?
	Time. The time you spend on your work is about you. Describe the time you spend each day on your research.
45	How many hours a day do you spend on average? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-4 • 4-8 • 8-10
46	How many hours a day do you use your computer? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-4 • 4-8 • 8-10
47	How do you plan your workday?
48	On a scale of 1 to 5, how much time does it take to stress and fatigue? 1 2 3 4 5
49	Why?
50	On a scale of 1 to 5, how much time do you spend searching ancient manuscripts and texts? 1 2 3 4 5
51	In relation to your previous answers, would you rather spend more time using Analog (manuscripts, printed texts, etc.) or digital tools (OCR texts, databases, etc.)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analog • Digital
52	Why?
	New Knowledge. Show your creativity and suggest tools for a more effective use and consultation of sources.
53	Do your research sources come mainly from digitized texts or manuscripts? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manuscripts • Digitized texts
54	What are the advantages of reading a digitized text compared to a manuscript?
55	What are the advantages of reading a handwritten text compared to a digitized one?
56	For the consultation of texts, digitized or not, among the tools you currently do not have which you would like to use?
57	How do you think the latter can improve your research activity?

58	In particular, if you wanted to identify or compare data within texts, what digital tools (software, websites, etc.) would you use?
59	Do you think it's hard to track data in text? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
60	Why?
61	In digitized manuscripts, could graphically visualizing concepts, contents and words, grasping logical connections, make your research more effective? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
62	Why?
63	What value do you place on scientific dissemination?

Tab. 1: First part of the WP8 questionnaire for potential users of uBIQUity.

The second part of the interview format (*Learning Styles. A survey of methods and strategies in personal data and information acquisition and processing for humanistic research*) consisted of two thematic sections: *Learning Styles* and *Learning Strategies*.

The *Learning Styles* section made it possible to identify the modes (multimodal or unimodal) employed in research activities. The *Learning Strategies* section revealed the channels most frequently used for acquiring and processing information.

The questions used in this second part of the interview process are listed below.

TAB. 2	
	Learning Styles. A survey of methods and strategies in personal data and information acquisition and processing for humanistic research
	Background information
1	E-mail
2	Age <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25-35 • 35-45 • 45-55 • 55-65

3	<p>What role do you play in the ITSERR project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PhD student ● Researcher ● Associate Professor ● Full Professor
4	SSD (Indicates your scientific disciplinary field of reference)
	<p>Scientific research. Select the answers you think most relevant and best exemplify your preferences. If necessary, you can select more than one answer.</p>
5	<p>How do you start a new research project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Brainstorm by pinning keywords. B. Share your ideas with colleagues to get their feedback. C. Read more articles. D. Research and study primary sources in libraries, foundations or archives.
6	<p>What kind of sources do you use to write an article?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Iconographic sources. B. Oral sources. C. Written sources. D. Case studies and material sources.
7	<p>How do you prefer to present your research results?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Prepare a presentation you can project. B. Organize a conference or attend a conference/round table. C. Prepare a report and/or write a scientific paper. D. Organize laboratory activities.
8	<p>You take part in a conference as a speaker, how do you prepare yourself?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Prepare diagrams and diagrams to support the presentation. B. Note some keywords and review your speech several times. C. Write your speech and learn it by reading it several times. D. You rely on case studies or clarifying examples.
	<p>Readings and notes. Select the answers you think most relevant and best exemplify your preferences. If necessary, you can select more than one answer.</p>
9	<p>How do you develop your research at libraries, foundations or archives?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Supporting iconographic research. B. Listening to audio material. C. Comparison of manuscripts to highlight similarities and differences. D. Collection of material sources.
10	<p>Attend a conference, how do you take your notes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Make summary diagrams using colors to highlight relevant sections. B. Record the intervention of the rapporteur. C. Transcribe the speech using lists and annotations. D. Note only the case studies submitted.
11	<p>After studying a handwritten text, what do you store more easily?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Iconographic apparatus, typography, colours, white space of the page. B. Shared summary information with a colleague. C. Critical apparatus and appendices. D. Binding, paper, presence of inserts.

12	<p>What do you do before a term you don't know?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Focus the graphemes that make it up. B. Listen to the pronunciation. C. You use the dictionary to trace the root. D. Try to reconstruct the situation in which the term is used.
<p>Digital reworkings and experiences. Select the answers you think most relevant and best exemplify your preferences. If necessary, you can select more than one answer.</p>	
13	<p>You are using a new digital tool that allows you to view text annotations through patterns and graphical configurations; what do you think can help you understand data?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Customize the structure of the graphic scheme, highlighting keywords, using different shapes and colors, and creating visual links between individual graphemes or between parts of speech. B. Listen to the pronunciation of a term in the display. C. Display data using lists, bullet points and explanatory notes. D. Convert a 2D visualization into 3D so that you can study its structure in its entirety and more easily grasp logical-transversal links.
14	<p>A colleague of yours told you that there is a software useful for the reworking of your notes and their consultation. Would you like to deepen the functionality; how do you document yourself?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Search the network for visual diagrams of how the software works. B. Discuss this with your colleague and let him describe the main features to you. C. Read articles and reviews. D. Install the software on your PC and test it.
15	<p>What, in your opinion, is necessary for a website/app/software to search?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Intuitive interface. B. In-depth video or audio channels. C. Sections with comments or reviews from other certified users. D. Interactive activities.
16	<p>What digital tools make your search faster?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Platforms for data processing through diagrams and diagrams (e.g. Miro, Obsidian ...). B. Platforms that use artificial intelligence and allow you to start a conversation by asking questions (e.g. ChatGPT ...). C. Note-taking platforms for editing notes through annotation lists (e.g. Scrintal, Notion ...). D. Platforms that allow you to create interactive archives (e.g. digital collections of primary sources ...).
<p>New knowledge. Select the answers you think most relevant and best exemplify your preferences. If necessary, you can select more than one answer.</p>	
17	<p>What new tools do you think could improve the functionality of websites/apps/search software?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Set for creating diagrams, tables, and graphs for text annotation. B. Audio channels for listening to podcasts and interviews. C. Links to in-depth articles. D. Possibility to ask questions or discuss with industry experts.
18	<p>What activities do you propose to support the publication of a scientific paper?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Creation of an iconographic apparatus that supports the text and that can explain the themes dealt with. B. Participation in conferences as a rapporteur. C. Recording podcasts on the topic covered and sharing on specialized platforms. D. Preparation of laboratory activities.

19	<p>What digital tools could help you build new knowledge?</p> <p>A. Tools representing logical-transversal connections of the research topics investigated. B. Chat and messaging apps to engage with industry experts (e.g., Slack ...). C. Consultation of lists of scientific publications. D. d. Platforms for the consultation of digital archives.</p>
20	<p>What digital tools could suggest new research questions?</p> <p>1. Tools that graphically process data extracted from a conversation with AI systems. 2. Chatbot based on AI. 3. Tools that allow you to track and consult scientific articles related to your research theme. 4. In-depth webinars.</p>

	Learning Strategies. Indicates how often you use the research strategies described
1	<p>Customize your research notes using a personal visual code (e.g. colors, patterns, sketches, images or places it ...).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
2	<p>Highlight semantic relationships (synonyms, semantic families ...) using arrows or connection marks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
3	<p>Insert notes between the pages of the text you are viewing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
4	<p>Carefully observe the layout and the graphical elements within a text page.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
5	<p>You will dwell on the images accompanying the text you are consulting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
6	<p>You focus on symbols and signs in the text you are reading.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always

7	<p>You don't like taking notes and your written notes are lacking.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
8	<p>You have a very good memory in remembering anecdotes, and orally transmitted stories.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
9	<p>Use audio recorders in your research activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
10	<p>Listen to podcasts and interviews.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
11	<p>During a meeting, you ask questions or open debates.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
12	<p>Submit your ideas to your colleagues, because you believe that dialogue is a fundamental tool for an exchange of knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
13	<p>Take notes to keep track of what you've heard.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
14	<p>Organize your notes into lists, bullet points, and hierarchical categories.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always

15	<p>In your notes you write down a concept in an interactive way, using other words and transcribing concepts in a different way.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
16	<p>You prefer to turn information and data into graphs, diagrams into word streams.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
17	<p>Use definitions to explain new concepts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
18	<p>Before a conference, read your notes several times to better define the key concepts of your talk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
19	<p>Take frequent breaks during the research activity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
20	<p>When preparing an intervention during a conference or lesson, show many explanatory examples.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
21	<p>To verify the veracity of a given research case study, you research case studies that can support your thesis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
22	<p>Research manuscripts and artifacts are designed to be viewed in person.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
23	<p>Create iconographic collections with photographs and images for your research.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always

24	Organize laboratory activities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● never ● sometimes ● often ● always
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Tab. 2: Second part of the WP8 questionnaire for potential users of uBIQUity.

The entire questionnaire was administered as an activity during the ITSERR meeting held in Palermo in February 1-2, 2024, with the aim of identifying new design strategies for improving the use of information. The responses were subsequently processed and standardized in an Excel matrix, producing an initial representative sample and yielding valid qualitative findings that can inform the development of a tool genuinely tailored to the needs of humanists.

4.2 User Stories

A user story is a brief description of a product feature from the end-user’s perspective. Its goal is to describe the value that the user will get from a given feature without focusing immediately on technical details. A user story is usually structured in a simple form:

As [user role], I want [action or goal] so [reason or benefit].

In essence:

- Who: the end user who needs it.
- What: the need to be satisfied or action to be carried out.
- Why: the benefit or motivation.

To be effective, user stories must be structured in a way that is understandable by all stakeholders involved: researchers, designers, and developers. They will first be used by designers to build wireframes and prototypes of the functionality that can then be reworked or further developed during handoff to developers.

The output includes:

- Initiative (project)
- Epic
- Title of the User Story
- Who (user role)
- Description (what and why)
- Acceptance Criteria

- Priority (of functionality versus product objective).

Acceptance criteria are a set of conditions that a user story must meet to be considered complete. These criteria define the functional and non-functional requirements that the product or feature must satisfy to meet user expectations and be accepted by the customer or development team. More precisely, these criteria:

- drive design and development: They provide teams with a clear understanding of what needs to be built and user expectations.
- define the boundaries: They set the limits of what is included in the user story, preventing the inclusion of elements out of scope.
- help in validation: They serve as a basis for functional tests before, during and after the release, allowing us to verify if the implemented functionality meets the expectations described in the user story.

Fig. 2: The structure of the user stories.

According to this method the WP8 team produced the user stories described in the following table:

TAB. 3					
User Stories					
Initiative	Epic	Title	As A	Description	Acceptance Criteria
WP8-uBIQUity Arabic	Dataset	Arabic Corpus	Researcher	I want to have a Corpus featured by data and metadata readable by both backend and frontend. By using a structured corpus, we can create hierarchy in the UI, create different reading levels, and suggest which visualization mode to use.	<p>The Arabic corpus consists of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qur’ān 2. Ḥadīth 3. Sirah 4. Tafsīr <p>Each text is featured by metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qur’ān <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 Sūrah number <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1.1 Sūrah title 1.2 Āyah number 2. Ḥadīth <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Author of the collection <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1 Date of birth 2.1.2 Date of death 2.1.3 Place of birth 2.1.4 Place of death 2.1.5 Main place of activity 2.2 Title of the collection <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1 Date of release (<i>original work</i>) 2.3 Book number <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.3.1 Book title 2.4 Chapter number <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.4.1 Chapter title 2.5 Ḥadīth number 2.6 Publication details (<i>modern edition</i>) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.6.1 Editor 2.6.2 Publisher 2.6.3 Volume number 2.6.4 Place of release 2.6.5 Date of release 3. Sirah <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 Author of the biography <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1.1 Date of birth 3.1.2 Date of death 3.1.3 Place of birth 3.1.4 Place of death 3.1.5 Main place of activity 3.2 Title of the biography <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.2.1 Date of release (<i>original work</i>) 3.2.2 Place of release (<i>original work</i>) 3.3 Publication details (<i>modern edition</i>) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.3.1 Editor 3.3.2 Publisher 3.3.3 Volume number 3.3.4 Place of release 3.3.5 Date of release

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Tafsīr 4.1 Author of the commentary <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1.1 Date of birth 4.1.2 Date of death 4.1.3 Place of birth 4.1.4 Place of death 4.1.5 Place of activity 4.2 Title of the commentary <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.2.1 Date of release (<i>original work</i>) 4.2.2 Place of release (<i>original work</i>) 4.3 Qur'ānic reference <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.3.1 Sūrah number 4.3.2 Āyah number 4.4 Publication details (<i>modern edition</i>) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.4.1 Editor 4.4.2 Publisher 4.4.3 Volume number 4.4.4 Place of release 4.4.5 Date of release
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<p>WP8-uBIQUity Greek</p>	<p>Dataset</p>	<p>Greek Corpus</p>	<p>Researcher</p>	<p>I want to have a Corpus featured by data and metadata readable by both backend and frontend. By using a structured corpus, we can create hierarchy in the UI, create different reading levels, and suggest which visualization mode to use.</p>	<p>The Greek corpus consists of</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bible Versions 2. A selection of Commentaries on Bible Versions <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. For the Bible Versions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Name of Bible Version <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1.1 Chronology (century/s) 1.1.2 Geography (area) 1.2 Edition <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.1 Title 1.2.2 Editor 1.2.3 Volume numbers and specific volume of the text 1.2.4 Place of release and Publisher 1.2.5 Date of release 1.2.6 Total Book Number 1.2.7 Book Titles 1.2.8 Total number of Chapters 1.2.9 Total number of Verses 1.2.10 Apparatus <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.10.1 Total number of Apparatus (min 1, max 2) 1.2.10.2 Types of Apparatus (min 1, max 2) 1.2.10.3 Apparatus Preface and Signatures 2. For the selection of Commentaries on Bible Versions <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Author <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1 Date of birth 2.1.2 Date of death 2.1.3 Place of birth 2.1.4 Place of death 2.1.5 Place of activity 2.2 Title of the Commentary <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1 Date of release 2.2.2 Place of release 2.3 Edition <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.3.1 Title 2.3.2 Editor 2.3.3 Volume numbers and specific volume of the text 2.3.4 Place of release and Publisher 2.3.5 Date of release 2.3.6 Total Book Number 2.3.7 Book Titles 2.3.8 Total number of Chapters 2.3.9 Total number of Paragraph 2.3.10 Total number of sections/lines 2.3.11 Apparatus <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.3.11.1 Total number of Apparatus 2.3.11.2 Types of Apparatus 2.3.11.3 Apparatus Preface and Signatures
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<p>WP8-uBIQUity Latin</p>	<p>Dataset</p>	<p>Latin Corpus</p>	<p>Researcher</p>	<p>I want to have a Corpus featured by data and metadata readable by both backend and frontend. By using a structured corpus, we can create hierarchy in the UI, create different reading levels, and suggest which visualization mode to use.</p>	<p>The Latin corpus consists of</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bible Versions 2. A selection of Commentaries on Bible Versions <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. For the Bible Versions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Name of Bible Version <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1.1 Chronology (century/s) 1.1.2 Geography (area) 1.2 Edition <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.1 Title 1.2.2 Editor 1.2.3 Volume numbers and specific volume of the text 1.2.4 Place of release and Publisher 1.2.5 Date of release 1.2.6 Total Book Number 1.2.7 Book Titles 1.2.8 Total number of Chapters 1.2.9 Total number of Verses 1.2.10 Apparatus <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.10.1 Total number of Apparatus (min 1, max 2) 1.2.10.2 Types of Apparatus (min 1, max 2) 1.2.10.3 Apparatus Preface and Signatures 2. For the selection of Commentaries on Bible Versions <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Author <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1 Date of birth 2.1.2 Date of death 2.1.3 Place of birth 2.1.4 Place of death 2.1.5 Place of activity 2.2 Title of the Commentary <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1 Date of release 2.2.2 Place of release 2.3 Edition <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.3.1 Title 2.3.2 Editor 2.3.3 Volume numbers and specific volume of the text 2.3.4 Place of release and Publisher 2.3.5 Date of release 2.3.6 Total Book Number 2.3.7 Book Titles 2.3.8 Total number of Chapters 2.3.9 Total number of Paragraph 2.3.10 Total number of sections/lines 2.3.11 Apparatus <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.3.11.1 Total number of Apparatus 2.3.11.2 Types of Apparatus 2.3.11.3 Apparatus Preface and Signatures
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WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Dataset	Filtering	Researcher	I want to filter results to fine-tune the research	I must have the possibility to choose filters from these following groups: 1. Authorship: check boxes to select authors 2. Source: check boxes to select sources 3. Temporal: a range slider to select a period 4. Spatial: wireframe map thumbs to select regions 5. Categorical: check to select Scripture and Commentary 6. Semantics: check boxes to select exact, inflections, roots, synonyms, contrary, topic fields, structures 7. Text/Apparatus
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Text Comparis on	Searching	Researcher	I want to search for a text string in a Corpus (Scriptures and Commentaries) to locate it	I must have the possibility to: 1. Insert the text string or a single term in a search field 1.2 The search field must be featured by the autocomplete 2. Set semantic criteria (exact, inflections, roots, synonyms, contrary, topic fields, structures) 2.1 Select one or more comparison types: (a) Text to Text, (b) Text to Apparatus, (c) Apparatus to Apparatus 2.2 If (b) or (c) options are selected --> Switch on/off Apparatus Types 3. And/Or choose filters (grouped by topics: title, author, chronology, geolocation) 4. See results as a list and the list item count 5. Switch to another visualization according to the selected filters 6. Review filters to finetune results 7. Order the list according to chronological order (author) and/or the total percentage of similarity 8. Access to "Comparison modes"
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Text Comparis on	Browsing	Researcher	I want to select a text from the corpus for close reading	I must have the possibility to: 1. See the list item count 2. Scroll the list items of the corpus 3. Or use an autocomplete search field to insert a title to filter the list 4. Or filter the list according to author, chronology, geolocation 5. Order the list according to chronological order (author) 6. Select a text to read it 6.1 Access to the "Searching" 6.2 Switch on/off Apparatus view 7. Select a text string to access the "Searching" auto-filling the search field

WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Text Comparis on	Searching	Researcher	Search cmd+F	
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Text Comparis on	Results	Researcher	I want each result to be featured with a content and a list of attributes. Each attribute is useful in defining results as information entities that contain content, style, function, and behavior.	Each result must have: 1 A content: a single word or a string 1.1 If it's a single term I want to access to existing and external lexical/morphological resources 2. Categorical Attributes: Autorship, Source, Temporal, Spatial 3. Labels: scripture or commentary 4. Semantic Tag: exact, inflections, roots, synonyms, contrary, topic fields, structures 5. Apparatus Type Tag 6. The percentage of similarity (Total, Text to Text, Text to Apparatus, Apparatus to Apparatus) 7. The ratio between the amount of matching terms and the total 8. Link to "Bibliographical references" 9. An icon link to the Reference page
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Bibliogra phical Referenc es	General Library of Bibliographi cal References	Researcher	I want each result to be featured with a Zotero's list of bibliographical references with tagged items because I want a guide to interpret results	I must have the possibility to: 1. Access to a Zotero's list of bibliographical references clicking on each result or its features (ex: I can click on an author name to open the related bibliographical references) 2. Each item of the list must be tagged 2.1 An autocomplete feature will suggest the most common tags in use 3. Contribute to the list in order to add new bibliographical references using Zotero's API 4. Save one or more items to my "Personal Library of Bibliographical References"
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Bibliogra phical Referenc es	Personal Library of Bibliographi cal References	Researcher	I want to have a personal library of bibliographical references because I want to manage different lists of referencences according to my workflows	I must have the possibility to: 1. Order the bibliographical references in different lists 1.1 Each list must have a specific name 1.2 Each list can have a brief description 2. See how each item has been linked to my workflows 3. Take personal notes on each item
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Contextu al Note System	Contextual Note- Taking	Researcher	I want to take contextual notes on each content of the workflow because I need to comment on my actions for myself and other users.	I must have the possibility to: 1. Take personal notes on each content 2. Write the note using Markdown markup language 3. Tag the note 4. Assign the note to other users 4.1 Receive an email notification once the assignment is done 5. Manage notes
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Contextu al Note System	Contextual Note- Managemen t	Researcher	I want to manage my contextual notes because I need to quickly retrieve information	I must have the possibility to: 1. Have a list of my notes 1.1 The list is ordered by tags, assignments, and workflows

WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Text Comparis on	Comparison Modes	Researcher	I want to select results to compare	I must have the possibility to: 1. Select items from the result list 2. Run the comparison 3. See the Results 3.1 The percentage of similarity (Total, Text to Text, Text to Apparatus, Apparatus to Apparatus) 4. Switch to different visualization according to the filters
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Data visualizat ion	Close Reading	Researcher	I want to read results using different close reading modes. Close reading is crucial to analyze results in their context. Different kinds of modes are needed because only one would return a partial view	I must have the possibility to switch between the following modes: 1. Single Context Page View (text+apparatus) 1.1 In this mode I can switch on the Scripture references highlights 1.1.1 With mouse hover a tooltip will show a preview of the source and a link to it 2. Parallel View (of max 3 columns) 3. Variant Graph 4. Single terms comparisons (link to external tools/service) 5. Vectorial Visualization 6. Single term view
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Data visualizat ion	Distant Reading	Researcher	I want to explore results using different distant reading modes. Distant reading is crucial to analyze results as structures and patterns.	I must have the possibility to switch between the following modes: 1. Heatmap View 2. Vectorial Visualization
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Stats Reading	Single Term Search	Researcher	I want to search for only one term because I need to be able to start my research from a single term	I must have: 1. A single term search field 1.2 The search field is featured by an autocomplete This research links to the "Single Term view"
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Stats Reading	Single Term View	Researcher	I want to have a page for the single term to have an overview of its use	For the single term, I must have: 1 List of its readings (variant readings) 1.1 I can filter readings by Apparatus types 2 External lexica resources 3. The frequency of the term in the whole Corpus 4. The frequency of the term in a list of single texts (text+apparatus) in decreasing order 5. The geolocation of the term
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Flow Recordin g	Version Visualazing	Researcher	I want to visualize each version of the research flow in real-time because the goal of the platform is not only to find solutions provided by AI but also to share reasonings with the community.	I must have the possibility to: 1. Keep track of all the actions taken (searching, browsing, filtering, ordering, selections, comparisons, ...) 1.1 Edit each action to generate new flows of the research saving the previous ones 1.2 Visualize each flows to compare 2. Save flows 3. Share flows with the platform

					[We suggest a Node-based UI]
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Flow Recording	Repository	Researcher	I want a repository to save different version of my research and browse other's ones to : 1. keep track of my reasoning overtime 2. let me restore old versions 3. let me compare versions 4. share versions with the community	I must have the possibility to: 1. Access to a personal page that contains my research versions 2. Visualize my contributions to the each version using heatmaps 3. Compare differences between versions [We suggest a GitHub-like approach]
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Validation	Feedback Modes	Researcher	I want to give feedback on the results to: 1. fine-tune AI 2. provide information to peers	I must have the possibility to: 1. Add notes to comment results 2. Rate the results
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	General Settings	Account setting	Researcher	I want to have an account page to set general account settings	I must have the possibility to: 1. Set my research as Public/Private 2. Invite other users to collaborate 3. Create a link to share my research
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	General Settings	Flow setting	Researcher	I want to have a panel to set my default flow	I must have the possibility to: 1. Select default Scriptures for comparison 2. Choose the default AI version
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	General Settings	Accessibility setting	Researcher	I want to have a panel to set accessibility features	I must have the possibility to: 1. Change the font-size 2. Switch between dark mode and light mode
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Export results	File formats	Researcher	I want to export my research/s to interoperable file format because we need to: 1. provide FAIR data 2. create reports outside the platform	I must have the possibility to export to: 1. Markdown 2. CSV 3. JSON 4. DOC 5. PDF The data structures and layouts of these files must be identified as ITSERR documents.
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Onboarding	Tours and tutorials	Researcher	I want to be contextually guided during my first access because I need an overview about how I can operate with the platform	I must have the possibility to: 1. Switch off the guide 1.2 Switch off the guide for the next access 2. Know the total amount of guide's step 3. Follow the guide step by step 4. Be linked to the "Reference" section We suggest using micro-copies to let the user be aware during the flow.

WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Support	FAQ	Researcher	I want to have a FAQ page to answer the most common questions and link the user to the Reference section for more in-depth reading.	I must have the possibility to: 1. Access to a accordion component listing the questions 1.2 All the accordion are collapsed by default The questions must groupes by topics
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Support	Reference Index	Researcher	I want to have a Reference section to provide a more in-depth reading. Micro-copies and FAQ must be linked to this section	I must have the possibility to: 1. Browse topics using an index
WP8-uBIQUity Latin / Greek / Arabic	Support	Single Page Reference	Researcher	I want to have a Single Page Reference to provide all the critical information about a topic	I must have the possibility to: 1. Quickly access to information 2. Learning efficiently by examples 3. Share the page 4. Access to related contents

Tab. 3: The WP8 user stories.

These user stories reflect the specialized nature of *uBIQUity*'s research questions, while also accommodating the diverse needs, learning styles and strategies of various users from different research fields, who may bring new perspectives and pose novel questions to the tool developed by WP8. It is intended to be a springboard for knowledge, not a cage that confines it.

4.3 Textual Analysis and Structural Formalization

Formalizing the structures of the ancient texts to be used on the *uBIQUity* platform is crucial for three main reasons. First, the dataset must accurately reflect the established structures recognized by experts in the field, while also allowing for modifications made possible by the digital environment—adjustments that are not feasible in the paper format. Second, each structural component functions as an information unit that conveys content, is situated within a context, and can operate according to specific functions. Third, each unit can be visually represented as an element of the user interface.

We began by formalizing the structures of the sacred texts, the Bible(s) and the Qur'ān, together with selected ancient exegetical works, using their reference editions as detailed in D8.1.1. Since our research is concerned with textual granularity, and therefore, especially in the case of biblical texts, takes into account the significant variant readings transmitted through direct or indirect tradition, the WP8 team has, on a trial basis, formalized and semantically enriched with metadata the apparatus of the book of Genesis from an edition of the Greek Bible (R_LXX) and an edition of the Latin Bible (W_VULG; for these abbreviations, see deliverable D8.1.1). The *uBIQUity* tool reserves an important space for

apparatus, as will be shown in *section 6*, dedicated to the different visualization modes on our platform.

We intend to visually present the biblical text as a deep and granular entity, shaped by historical, linguistic, literary, and interpretative complexity. In this way, the *uBIQUity* project attempts to offer a valuable countermeasure to fundamentalist approaches.

5. Findings

5.1 User Research: Spaces, Tools, Time, and New Knowledge

The results of the first part of the WP8 questionnaire are listed below according to the six thematic sections of the interview format [see *section 4.1* of this document]:

- Background Information
- Context
- Spaces
- Tools
- Time
- New Knowledge.

Background Information and Context

As previously noted [cf. *section 4.1*], the questionnaire was filled out by 29 scholars, both internal and external to the ITSERR project, specializing in the Humanities. The following section presents some statistics on the survey participants:

Academic Positions:

- Researchers: 76.5%
- PhD fellows: 11.9%
- Associate Professors: 5.8%
- Full Professors: 5.8%

Disciplinary Areas:

- Antiquities, philology, literary studies, art history:
- Classical Philology
- Ancient Christian Literature
- Medieval and Humanistic Latin Literature

- Anatolian Studies
- Hebrew Studies
- History of Islamic Countries
- Armenian, Caucasian, Mongolian, and Turkish Studies
- Philosophies and Religions of India and East Asia
- Oriental Languages and Cultures
- Historical, Philosophical, Pedagogical, and Psychological Sciences:
- Medieval History
- History of Christianity and Churches
- Archival Studies, Bibliography, and Library Science
- History of Medieval Philosophy
- Legal and Political Sciences:
- History of Medieval and Modern Law
- History and Institutions of Asia

Age:

- 25–35 years: 41.18%
- 35–45 years: 29.41%
- 45–55 years: 29.41%

Nationality:

- Italian: 94.12%
- Non-Italian: 5.88%

The collected results were standardized and reorganized in an Excel matrix, enabling the identification of a representative sample of researchers engaged in humanities studies.

Spaces

The investigation prioritized the spatial characteristics of locations used for research activities, whether conducted in-person or remotely. By analyzing the environment and its relationship with the researchers, habits and behaviors were reconstructed. The workspace emerged as a key factor in understanding research methodologies and strategies.

In-Person Activities:

Universities and libraries were the most frequently used spaces, preferred by 40.74% of respondents, compared to archives and foundations, which accounted for 18.52%. Work environments equipped with large desks and bookshelves, suitable for consulting physical materials, were considered essential. Notably, 40.18% of researchers emphasized the need for spacious desks for bibliographic research, suggesting that digital tools are often viewed as supplementary to the consultation of analog sources.

Remote Activities:

The data revealed that 94.12% of scholars conducted research remotely. Remote workspaces were described as predominantly quiet, well-lit, and comfortable. However, the lack of reference materials and limited opportunities for collaboration with colleagues were identified as significant challenges.

Preferred Methods:

- In-person: 17.65%
- Remote: 5.88%
- Both: 76.47%

Comfortable Methods:

- In-person: 29.42%
- Remote: 35.29%
- Both: 35.29%

Importance of Workspaces:

- Not Important: 0%
- Somewhat Important: 0%
- Important: 35.29%
- Very Important: 64.71%

Functionality of Workspaces:

- Not Important: 0%
- Somewhat Important: 0%
- Important: 29.41%
- Very Important: 70.59%

Comfort of Workspaces:

- Not Important: 5.88%
- Somewhat Important: 0%
- Important: 35.31%
- Very Important: 58.81%

Tools

Targeted questions made it possible to identify the tools researchers use and consider indispensable. The following categories were highlighted:

- Digital tools
- Audio recording devices
- Tools for reproducing iconographic sources

The analysis of the documented responses reveals the predilection of humanists for recording qualitative and quantitative data using personalized visual channels (verbal and non-verbal) and analog annotation methods. Notes, annotations, lists, definitions and customizable signs can be useful tools for the researcher to enhance the use and dissemination of textual and paratextual data and information.

Fig. 3:

The graph illustrates the learning strategies employed by humanist researchers to acquire data and information. Verbal strategies, such as creating word lists, using definitions to clarify concepts, generating word streams, and making annotations, are preferred by scholars who have identified significant responses in the verbal-visual channel (R=Read/Write in the VARK model).

Fig. 4:

The graph illustrates the learning strategies employed by humanist researchers to acquire data and information. Strategies such as creating visual code, using underlining, signs, and highlights are preferred

by scholars who have identified significant responses in the non-verbal visual channel (V=Visual in the VARK model).

This acquired knowledge is then processed using digital annotation tools. Digital tools contribute to a hierarchical and structured organization of concepts, thereby accelerating document production and significantly curtailing compilation time. The mechanization of processes, combined with data and metadata storage, in conjunction with the potential for multi-spatial and instrumental pole connections, enables the production of documents that are complex, precise, and readily shareable.

On the other hand, analog tools retain a pivotal role in transcribing acquired information. The ability to craft visual-verbal visualizations inherent in writing is limited by the mechanical annotation of data using digital devices such as computers. Luciano Perondi and Leonardo Romei point out that computerized writing has reintroduced a linearist bias, making it more difficult to compose non-rigidly sequential texts (Perondi, Romei 2010). The inability to incorporate characters beyond the basic set, coupled with the inability to dynamically organize text in space, results in semantic impoverishment. To address these challenges, tools such as iPads are emerging as alternatives, replicating the spatial organization and holistic visualization of text associated with analog practices.

The re-evaluation of data and information through visual-verbal connections, encompassing arrangement, orientation, size, etc., grants an enhanced value and meaning to the written word, with space emerging as one of the central dimensions of writing that could allow for the most interesting developments (Perondi 2012).

Analog Tools Usage:

- Solely Analog: 35.29%
- Primarily Analog with Digital: 35.39%
- Combined Analog and Digital: 29.32%

Annotating Analogically While Using Computers:

- Yes: 64.71%
- No: 35.29%

Digital Proficiency:

- Basic: 17.65%
- Sufficient: 35.29%

- Good: 41.18%
- Excellent: 5.88%

Digital Interface Intuitiveness:

- Intuitive: 64.71%
- Somewhat Intuitive: 5.88%
- Not Intuitive: 29.41%

Improving Digital Texts:

- Yes: 82.35%
- No: 17.65%

Time

Although digital tools facilitate dynamic and multi-instrumental information processing, analog tools were regarded as more convenient to use. Notably, 35.29% of scholars expressed a preference for dedicating more time to analog research tools. Direct engagement with unprocessed artifacts allowed researchers to analyze in depth and extract new, previously unclassified data.

New Knowledge

In the final section of the first part of the WP8 questionnaire, scholars were asked to envision new design scenarios to improve the research efficiency in terms of content and usability. Some of the proposed strategies included:

- Tools simulating analog consultation experiences
- Personalized annotations on digital texts
- Digital libraries
- Hypertextual connections between sources

A striking 94.12% of respondents affirmed that graphically visualizing concepts, content, and words to capture cross-disciplinary connections would significantly enhance research effectiveness. Customizable graphic data representations, along with the ability to retrieve both direct and indirect information hierarchically across multiple levels, were identified as essential for advancing research analysis and facilitating textual comparisons.

The observations and data collected underscore the need to design more effective and intuitive tools to improve the use of data and information in scientific research. At the same

time, in developing new computational tools, it is crucial to preserve the interpretative and collaborative dimensions of research, since without them genuine progress in knowledge cannot be achieved.

5.2 User Stories: Describing the Emerging Needs of the Scientific Community in Intertextuality Research

The user stories collected by the entire *uBIQUity* team confirm that the workflow is not linear when comparing texts and that qualitative results are more important than quantitative ones. Several pieces of evidence highlight this aspect, including the need to comment on and rate results, the ability to switch from close reading to distant reading (see Moretti 2000*a-b*, and 2003), and the capacity to access texts through browsing and searching.

Since these needs are very subjective, the *uBIQUity*'s interface must be flexible in terms of interactions and data visualization. We have investigated the potential of node-based UI to test new interactions that allow us to track the subjective actions performed by the researchers during their work and their interactions with AI, ideally allowing for a “performative reading” and a customizable, hierarchical interface identified by the user stories. We will share these workflows on a platform to track the entire thought processes in a collaborative research context.

As Johanna Drucker states, the diagrammatic language has “generative possibilities” that lead to a “performative” reading, where the reader changes the content structure by actively interacting with it (Drucker 2013).

Using a node-based UI is not new. It dates back to 1969 when the GRAIL Project (Graphical Input Language) was introduced. Its aim was to enhance programming processes by allowing users to draw objects freehand on a tablet. The system recognized these and transformed them into nodes capable of performing tasks and connecting to other nodes. It provided a way to build and manage workflows with a high degree of intimacy, enabling users to reach through the display and interact directly with information structures (Kay 1990).

Later, other node-based software platforms were released. They can be used without coding and have different purposes: music and sound composition (PureData), 3D modelling and shaders (Blender), and learning coding (Scratch), to mention a few among the many open-source ones. They share several common features in terms of user experience, like visual workflow, drag-and-drop nodes, non-linear editing, immediate feedback, modularity, scalability, and error handling and debugging. Today, new AI node-based tools are being developed to connect various agents and integrate external applications, enhancing productivity and automating batch processes—methods for executing a series of tasks on a computer system automatically without user interaction.

On the contrary, *uBIQUity* seeks to encourage user interaction and provide tools for “slowing down” the process rather than speeding it up.

6. Interacting with Knowledge: The *uBIQUity* Platform

The *uBIQUity* software will provide a workspace to create and connect nodes that have specific contents, functions, and behaviors. The objective is to build a design system where the components construct nodes in the workflow to accomplish tasks and visualize thinking processes. Researchers will set nodes for input content, select options, filter, visualize output, and embed external apps. Each node will have a degree of customization to meet the needs of potential scenarios that would be unknown in advance.

Moreover, researchers will evaluate their work by giving feedback on the results produced by AI. The bi-dimensional space of the workflow overcomes the limitations of the current AI text-based UI and facilitates the discovery of correlations between information that would be difficult to identify in a linear process.

As an example, consider a workflow whose purpose is to find intertextual references between the Latin Bible(s) in three different reference editions (source texts: W_VULG; B_VL; S_VL; for these abbreviations see D8.1.1) and a selected passage from Augustine’s commentary entitled *De Genesi ad litteram* (target text; its reference edition is Zycha 1894, CSEL 28,1).

To explore intertextuality, researchers need: (a) to launch a search for querying a textual passage according to one or more comparison criteria (*Exact, Inflections, Roots, Synonyms, Antonyms, Structures-AI*); (b) to visualize and order the list of sentence similarity results; (c) to choose from this list two or more results to compare in detail; and (d) to initiate the comparison between these selected texts [*Fig. 5*].

The screenshot displays the uBIQUity search engine interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ITSERR logo and project name, and a search bar. Below this, a breadcrumb trail shows 'Home / Tools / uBIQUity'. The main interface is divided into several sections:

- Search Progress:** Shows three steps: '1. Search Latin (18)', '2. Compare (3)', and '3. Search (4)'.
- Target Text:** A box labeled 'W_VULG | Genesis 1:2' containing the Latin text: 'Terra autem erat inanis et vacua, et tenebrae super faciem abyssi: et Spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas'.
- Comparison Criteria:** A section with buttons for 'Exact', 'Inflections', 'Roots', 'Synonyms', 'Antonyms', and 'Structures'.
- Search Results:** A list of results sorted by 'Similarity'. The first result is 'Genesis / Chapter: 1:2' with a similarity score of 234.08. It includes the text and a comparison of 'inanis' and 'faciem abyssi'.
- Comparison Criteria:** A section with buttons for 'Exact', 'Inflections', 'Roots', 'Synonyms', 'Antonyms', and 'Structures'.
- Search Results:** A list of results sorted by 'Similarity'. The first result is 'V_VL > GEN > 1:2' with a similarity score of 234.08. It includes the text and a comparison of 'inanis' and 'faciem abyssi'.
- Comparison Criteria:** A section with buttons for 'Exact', 'Inflections', 'Roots', 'Synonyms', 'Antonyms', and 'Structures'.
- Search Results:** A list of results sorted by 'Similarity'. The first result is 'V_SL > GEN > 1:2' with a similarity score of 234.08. It includes the text and a comparison of 'inanis' and 'faciem abyssi'.

Fig. 5: uBIQUity search engine.

At this stage, branches corresponding to the number of selected texts are automatically created. Each branch splits into two sub-branches: one for *Text-Text* comparison results and the other for *Text-Apparatus* comparison results (if there is no critical apparatus in the edition of the Bible under consideration or if this is not yet available due to copyright issues, this second sub-branch does not appear) [Fig. 6].

The screenshot displays the uBIQUity web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home / Tools / uBIQUity' and a search bar. Below this, a toolbar contains options like 'Save Flow', 'Share', 'Export', 'Flows', and 'New Search'. The main content area is titled 'Searched Text' and shows a comparison of three Latin scriptures from Genesis 1:2. The first scripture is 'W_VULG | Genesis 1:2' by Sofronio Eusebio Girolamo. The second is 'B_VL | Genesis 1:2' by Genesis. The third is 'S_VL | Genesis 1:2' by Johannes. Each scripture card displays the original Latin text and a 'Text Accuracy' score of 234,08. Below each card, there is a section for 'Apparatus Accuracy' with a score of 234,08. The interface also includes a 'Comparison Criteria (3)' dropdown menu and a 'Notes' section on the right.

Fig. 6: uBIQUity node-based user interface.

The accuracy rate (or fusion rate) suggests an insight path that can be read in two modes: distant reading and close reading. In distant reading mode, the maps reveal the quantity and the distribution of intertextual references between the compared texts [Fig. 7]. By clicking on a map element that includes the selected textual passage, the researcher can display this reference from time to time in its context of use.

Fig. 7: uBIQUity distant reading mode.

This quantitative approach then guides the researcher along specific research paths that can be further explored by switching to two close reading modes: a parallel comparison view and a variant graph. Parallel comparison serves as a vital tool for philologists by enabling them to analyze textual variant readings line by line [Fig. 8]. The parallel view replicates the experience of placing two or more books side by side on a table for comparison. As in the physical realm, this method becomes more elaborate when there are more than three volumes to consider.

The screenshot shows the ITSERR uBIQUity interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Projects', 'Events', 'News', 'People', 'Resources', and 'Support'. A search bar is located on the right. Below the navigation, there are tabs for '1. Search Latin (18)' and '2. Compare (3)'. The main content area displays a parallel comparison of three Latin texts from Genesis 1:2, attributed to Sofronio Eusebio Girolamo. The texts are shown in three columns. The first column shows the original text. The second and third columns show variations, with differences highlighted in yellow. The differences are: 'inanis' instead of 'inans', 'faciem abyssi' instead of 'faciem abyssi', and 'ferebatur' instead of 'ferebatur'. The interface also includes an 'Apparatus' section at the bottom of each column, which lists the differences. The 'Apparatus' section for the second and third columns shows the following differences: '- aquam' and 'Apparatus'.

Fig. 8: uBIQUity parallel comparison.

In this case, a variant graph can show terms that overlap or differ within more than three of compared texts [Fig. 9].

The screenshot shows the uBIQUity web interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Projects', 'Events', 'News', 'People', 'Resources', and 'Support'. A search bar is located on the right. Below the navigation, there are two search tabs: '1. Search Latin (18)' and '2. Compare (3)'. The main content area displays a variant graph for the Latin text 'Terra autem erat inanis et vacua, et tenebrae super faciem abyssi : et Spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas : et Spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas : et Spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas Terra autem erat inanis et vacua, et tenebrae'. The graph shows the alignment of terms across different versions of the text. The terms 'erant' and 'erant super abyssum' are highlighted in yellow, and their occurrences in different versions are listed in a table below the graph.

Line 1	Searched Text	Occurrences
T	1/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant
A	2/17 Witness A, +6	erant
A	2/17 Witness M, +3	erant
T	15/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant super abyssum
A	3/17 Witness T, +3	erant super abyssum
T	17/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant super abyssum

Line 2	Searched Text	Occurrences
T	1/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant
A	2/17 Witness A, +6	erant
A	2/17 Witness M, +3	erant
T	15/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant
A	3/17 Witness T, +3	erant
T	17/17 W_VULG Genesis 1:2	erant

Fig. 9: uBIQUity variant graph.

A tool such as *TRAViz* (*Text Re-Use Alignment Visualization*) visualizes variations between versions/editions of both ancient and modern texts (Schmidt, Colomb 2009). It is especially powerful for reading multiple versions of a text. It divides each version into individual terms (tokens), lines them up, and overlaps them like a subway map so the researcher can distinguish individual tracks (Jänicke, Geßner, Franzini *et alii* 2015).

Another possibility would be to process a single term according to computational linguistics analysis tools such as frequency graphs or word clouds. These tools are embedded in the nodes through an API (Application Programming Interface), which is a set of rules and protocols that allow different software applications to communicate with one another. Through these nodes, other research paths related to the previous one can be accessed, and new workflows can be created.

Returning to the search view, we can launch a new search—either in parallel with the first by setting a different comparison criterion (e.g., including roots or synonyms), or as a replacement by modifying the original query. In both cases, all actions are recorded and tracked in a node-based view.

Furthermore, notes can be attached both to the entire workflow and to each operation. The note has a field for plain text and one for entering primary and secondary bibliographical references. The platform allows for the retrieval, listing, and sharing of these notes. Note

taking and note management are powerful features that support the recording and tracking of the researcher’s reasoning.

7. Algorithms and IT tools

This section presents preliminary information on the novel tool developed by the *uBIQUity* team and on the outcomes of its use. Further details on these aspects will be provided in deliverable D8.1.3, which is devoted to demonstrating the effectiveness of the algorithms.

7.1 Greek Search Engine Evaluation for Intertextual Reference Retrieval

The *uBIQUity* team has developed a search engine to support intertextual research within the Greek Bible and between biblical texts and ancient exegetical works in Greek. The system retrieves biblical verses, enriched with textual variants, using both syntactic and semantic methods to enable flexible exploration of textual parallels.

The syntactic search applies language-agnostic techniques (e.g., word overlap, trigrams, shingles), while the semantic search leverages SPhilBERTa, a transformer model trained on Greek philosophical and theological texts, to produce vector embeddings for semantic similarity matching.

The system was evaluated using queries derived from intertextual references identified by humanist scholars between Clement of Alexandria’s works and the Septuagint Bible. Three search configurations—syntactic-only, embedding-only, and hybrid—were tested in both full corpus and subset modes.

Extended Evaluation of Search Configurations

Further controlled experiments explored different search strategies (token-based, language-agnostic, semantic, and hybrid) and the role of textual variants in retrieval effectiveness, assessed via standard information retrieval metrics.

7.2 Building *EnGraSept*: Towards an Adaptation of the Parser Output for the Semantic Web

WP8, in collaboration with the PRIN 2022 project *Resilient Septuagint*, is developing *EnGraSept* (*Enriched Granular Septuagint*), a dataset of the textual tradition of the Septuagint. At its core is a parser designed to extract structured data from .txt files of the critical apparatus of the *Göttingen Septuagint* and Rahlfs’ edition of the Septuagint (G_LXX and R_LXX, respectively; see D8.1.1 for these abbreviations) and to organize it so that philological information is represented in a machine-readable and semantically rich format.

To ensure interoperability and long-term reuse, the output is encoded in JSON-LD, a format compatible with *Elasticsearch* and directly convertible into RDF. Under the supervision of Carlo Meghini and Cesare Concordia (CNR-ISTI, Pisa), the model adapts and extends existing ontologies (*CAO*, *CEO*), introducing original elements under the provisional namespace *EnGraSept*. Beyond the apparatus itself, the model includes a dedicated structure for representing witnesses and their metadata.

A modeling effort parallel to *EnGraSept* is currently underway for the Weber-Gryson’s edition of the *Vulgate* (W_VULG), with the goal of aligning extracted Latin variants with *LiLa* lemmas (<https://lila-erc.eu>) and supporting future integration with lexical resources and semantic querying within the Latin biblical *corpus*.

7.3 Latin Search Engine for Intertextual Reference Retrieval

To support intertextual analysis within *uBIQUity*, we have developed a dedicated Latin search engine tailored for retrieving intertextual references in patristic literature. The system enables retrieval of biblical passages from the Vulgate (in Weber-Gryson’s edition = W_VULG) and the *Vetus Latina* (in Sabatier’s edition = S_VL), with a particular focus on identifying semantically aligned references within Augustine’s *De Genesi ad litteram* (in Zycha’s edition, 1894).

Each biblical verse is treated as a standalone retrievable unit, and retrieval is driven by dense vector embeddings that capture semantic relationships beyond simple lexical overlap. A core innovation of this work lies in the use of synthetic training data generated by GPT-4 to fine-tune Latin-specific embedding models (*i.e.* Latin BERT and LaBERTa in our experiments) using a contrastive learning framework. This approach addresses the low-resource nature of ancient Latin by generating controlled positive and negative passage pairs, allowing the models to better discriminate subtle semantic correspondences.

The resulting models demonstrated consistent and substantial gains in retrieval performance across these *corpora*, with particularly strong improvements observed in the most challenging cases of low lexical overlap. These results confirm the effectiveness of the synthetic data pipeline and its ability to generalize across distinct Latin textual traditions. Overall, the developed system constitutes a significant advancement toward scalable, semantically informed retrieval tools for the study of classical and historical Latin texts.

7.4 Arabic Search Engine for Intertextual Reference Retrieval

The search engine for the Arabic language has been specifically designed to support intertextual research across the core Arabic-language sources included in WP8, namely the Qur’ān, Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafāsīr*), and the *Sunna* (including both *ḥadīth* collections

and the *Sīrah al-nabawīyyah*). As of May 2025, a working version is available at the following link: <https://hadith2text.aimh.cloud.isti.cnr.it/>.

This tool enables users to filter results according to several metadata attributes, such as author, title of the work, dates of birth and death (in both the Hīgrī and Gregorian calendars), type of source, and others. The search index comprises 158 documents, including the Qur’ān, Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafāsīr*) from the 8th to the 15th centuries, and both canonical and non-canonical *ḥadīth* collections from Sunni and Shia traditions.

The index is constructed by chunking texts into fixed lengths of 500 characters with an overlap of 50 characters, allowing for fine-grained searches of short segments and enabling a nearly token-level study of the documents while preserving contextual information. In this way, scholars can identify relations and matches that are not strictly keyword-based or dependent on string matching, thereby facilitating novel discoveries. Initial testing found the tool satisfactory in terms of fidelity between queries and recovered matches, as well as potentially useful for testing research hypotheses. The search engine and interface are maintained as separate components, with the latter querying the former upon user request. As a result, the system can also be queried through an API, allowing for larger-scale experiments beyond those possible via the user interface.

8. Conclusions

uBIQUity is a significant advancement in the field of Digital Humanities and beyond, providing an innovative software for researching intertextual references between sacred texts and ancient Christian and Islamic exegetical works. The transdisciplinary approach, along with the integration of AI and human expertise, allows for enhanced precision and flexibility in research. However, the project must address challenges associated with managing data complexity and optimizing visualization tools.

Furthermore, to ensure effective use of the software, it will be crucial to provide continuous training and support for researchers. This includes attending workshops, seminars, and making educational resources available, so that users can make the most of *uBIQUity*’s capabilities and correctly interpret the data and results. We will focus on best practices for inclusion and accessibility, providing platform users with equivalent experience.

Evaluation and feedback from researchers are essential for the ongoing improvement of the software. Implementing a feedback management and performance monitoring system will allow for better adaptation of *uBIQUity* to the emerging needs of the scientific community of Religious Studies.

The goal of *uBIQUity* is not to replace biblical/patristic scholars or to compress the time needed for reflection in order to produce faster results. Rather, it seeks to advance knowledge by integrating the long-standing tradition of philological, historical, and exegetical research—without which no meaningful innovation would be possible—while

fostering greater dialogue with the scientific community and opening the way to new approaches and research questions.

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10. Publications

Publications authored by some members of the WP8 team and related to this specific deliverable (D8.1.2) are listed below:

- Caffagni, D., Cocchi, F., Mambelli, A., Tutrone, F., Zanella, M., Cornia, M., Cucchiara, R. (2025), “Generating Synthetic Data with Large Language Models for Low-Resource Sentence Retrieval”, in *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (Tampere, Finland, September 23-26, 2025)*, forthcoming.
- Costa, M. (2025), “Non-Linear Thinking Processes in Digital Humanities”, *Disegno industriale/Industrial Design (Diid)* 85, pp. 104–115: <https://doi.org/10.30682/diid8525h>.
- Costa, M. (2025), “uBIQUity Platform. Data Visualization for Digital Humanities”, in *Proceedings of 2CO Communicating Complexity Conference (Barcelona, July 3-5, 2024)*, forthcoming.
- D’Avenia, F., Ferrara, C., Costa, M., Palillo, C. (2024), “uBIQUity. Il design della comunicazione nel progetto ITSERR”, in G. di Bucchianico, A. Marano (a cura di), *Design per la diversità. Atti della conferenza annuale della Società italiana di Design (Pescara, 12-13 giugno 2023)*, Milano: Società Italiana di Design, pp. 369–377.

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